

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

D5.1 Evaluation of interaction components

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Project information

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOORBEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive summary

This deliverable provides a report on user interaction evaluation work conducted within task 5.1 of the project. This task involved providing user interface evaluation support to the pilots as well as carrying out evaluation work directly within this task. First, we overview the evaluation support provided to the pilots. This focussed on supporting pilot validation from a user interaction perspective. The rest of the deliverables describes studies of user interaction carried out within this task. First, we describe two studies into the process of cross-modal interpretation (termed Deep Listening) in which the user creates or makes sense of an experience combining music and visual art. The first study was conducted at a museum and involved participants in both creating and using cross-modal experiences. The second study was conducted online and investigated the types of association made between the music and visual art when during cross-modal experiences. Finally, the deliverable reports on an evaluation of tools for translating data into a Knowledge Graph, including SPARQL Anything which was extensively used within the project.

Document History

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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on work developing the evaluation protocols used to evaluate user interfaces and user experiences. This work was carried out in Task 1: Evaluation of interaction components carried out in WP5. This is part of the WP5 work on human interaction with musical heritage. More broadly, WP5 aims to provide design solutions for human-music interaction and support the needs of the WP1 pilots.

Section 2 describes support given to the pilots in the validation of user interaction components. Sections 3 and 4 describe two detailed evaluations carried out directly within this task. Section 3 describes experiments in a form of user experience we term Deep Listening, which involves simultaneously experiencing visual art and music. The software used to deliver the experiences both within the museum and online is described in deliverable D5.3. Section 4 describes an evaluation of tools for translating structured data to the Knowledge Graph. One of these tools, SPARQL Anything, was further developed in Polifonia and widely used by the WP1 Pilots for Knowledge Graph construction. Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

2. Methodological approach to pilot evaluation

One responsibility of this task was to select and develop evaluation protocols for use in the WP1 Pilots. As part of the WP1 pilot evaluation activities, each undertook validation of the approach. Validation comprised two main elements: validation of the quality of the data ingested in the Pilot application and the quality of the interface for accessing the data contained in the application. Support offered from WP5 was focussed on the second of these.

During the first year of the project, joint meetings and workshops were run across WP1 and WP5 to explore the range of evaluation protocols that could serve the purpose of supporting validation of the user interface. In selecting appropriate evaluation protocols for the pilots an emphasis was placed on standardised methods, that were relatively easy to administer. Given the methods would be used as part of an iterative design process rather than only as a final summative evaluation, consideration was given to methods that could provide rich feedback for relatively low effort in order to inform future stages of the design process.

The main methods that were discussed and presented and the meetings and workshops were:

- Structured interviews: Conducted with domain experts to understand their working practices and elicit feedback on early prototypes.
- Focus groups: Joint discussion with a number of stakeholders (e.g. target users of the application) to elicit feedback and priorities for development
- Surveys: Structured feedback from target users of the application. Incorporation of both quantitative feedback (e.g. rating of the proposed design) and qualitative feedback (e.g. open ended responses)
- Cognitive walkthroughs: Targets users working through defined tasks step-by-step to identify any difficulties in using the interface or elements of the interaction that worked well.

- Heuristic review: A structured walkthrough of the interface that also be conducted directly by the designers to identify any breakdowns in user interaction.
- AttrakDiff: Standardised survey instrument for assessing the aesthetic qualities of the interface
- SUS: Standardised survey instrument for accessing usability
- NASA TLX: Standardised survey instrument for measuring cognitive workload of carrying out tasks with the user interface.

Table 1 shows the range of evaluation methods used as part of the intermediate validation (see deliverables D1.4, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7). A range of methods were employed. As can be expected, given the formative evaluation conducted during the first half of the project, extensive use was made of methods such as interviews to elicit rich feedback from potential users as well as more structured approaches such as surveys to rate and comment on proposed designs.

Pilot	Intermediate evaluation methods
BELLS	Expert feedback interviews and questionnaire
ORGANS	Task completion and interview feedback by experts
INTERLINK	Online survey of potential adoption
FACETS	Expert feedback interviews
TONALITIES	User satisfaction questionnaire
TUNES	Expert interviews
MUSICBO	Focus group roundtable discussion with experts
CHILD	Heuristic evaluation
MEETUPS	Expert interview feedback on prototypes
ACCESS	User interviews and workshops

Table 1. User evaluation methods used to support the intermediate validation of pilots.

Evaluation methods used in the final validation of the pilots will be reported as part of the month-40 deliverable *Final ten-pilots validation report and lessons learned* (D1.8)

3. Evaluating Deep Listening in the museum and online

Previous work on the EU SPICE project explored the use of Citizen Curation to widen cultural participation at the Irish Museum of Modern Art (IMMA) (Mulholland et al 2023). This involved working with communities under-represented among museum visitors to develop and share their own perspectives on IMMA’s collection and exhibitions. These new perspectives on art can then be shared with other visitors, widening the range of voices included in the museum’s public offering and helping a broader range of potential visitors to connect art to their own lives and

concerns. The activities at the museum in which the communities participated had made use of the process of Slow Looking (Museum of Modern Art, Reed 2017, Tishman 2017) to help them engage with art and develop their own perspective. Slow Looking is a process that uses a series of prompts and questions to help the visitor to slow down and develop and share their own interpretation of the artwork.

Given the widespread passion for music, particularly among younger audiences who are underrepresented among museum visitors, this led to the question as to whether Citizen Curation, currently supported by a process of Slow Looking, could be expanded in which people from outside the museum could associate visual artworks with pieces of music, creating cultural experiences that involve not only looking but also listening. Combining music and visual art could potentially help museums to engage new audiences who would be able to develop and explore associations between visual art, with which they may be less familiar, and music, which is more likely to already play a significant role in their everyday cultural lives. As well as music being a potentially more familiar cultural form, research also suggests listening to music while looking at visual art can enhance the experience. Isaacson et al (2023) found that cross-modal experiences combining music and visual art, can help the observer to find new meaning and value.

3.1 Related work

3.1.1 Listening, emotion and mindfulness

Museums offer Slow Looking, or related methods such as Visual Thinking Strategies (VTS) (Visual Thinking Strategies 2024) to help the visitor interpret visual art. Cultural institutions do not offer equivalent methods for music or other auditory content, probably due to the predominance of visual art, and perhaps also due to music listening being a more familiar experience. However, research has considered how people make sense of music.

Given the value people place on music as a way of evoking emotion (Juslin 2008) a significant body of research has investigated how emotion is expressed and evoked through music. Juslin and Laukka (2004) investigate how emotion is conveyed through music by the composer and how those emotions are perceived by the listener. From a review of the literature, they observe that emotions are expressed using a combination of musical features in a probabilistic way. For example, anger may be expressed through a combination of features including fast tempo, minor mode, high sound level, small pitch variability and rhythmic changes. They note that a musical feature may be used in a similar manner in the expression of different emotions. For example, fast tempo can be used to communicate both anger and happiness. Emotions evoked in the listener may be rather different to those expressed by the composer, due in part to the social context in which music is consumed and the personal associations a listener makes between music and their lives. Hunter et al (2010) in their study of music and emotion distinguish between the listener's perception of emotion in music (essentially identification of the composer's intent) and the emotion they personally feel while listening. Although the two were correlated, perception ratings were more emotionally intense than feeling ratings.

Reybrouk (2017) argues that musical sense-making is an active process in which the listener creates their own associations between music and meaning rather than necessarily decoding the meaning intended by the composer. One factor that can be expected to affect musical sense-

making is the listener's familiarity with the type of music being played. Davies (2010) identifies the qualified listener as someone who is sufficiently familiar with a style of music to appreciate its expressiveness. Davies (2010) notes that most qualified listeners do not have formal music education but have acquired knowledge through exposure.

Bodie and Jones (2021) distinguish active listening and passive hearing, whether the source be music or another form of auditory information such as speech. Drawing on the dual process theory of reasoning (Evans 2004) they note that even active listening combines both fast, intuitive, unconscious processing as well as slow, deliberative, conscious processing. A listener may have an immediate, intuitive response to a piece of music which they combine and rationalise with slower, conscious processing of the music. Bodie and Jones (2021) note the relationship between being aware of these unconscious reasoning mechanisms and mindfulness (Brown and Ryan 2003) in which people try to access their unconscious reasoning and reflect on how it affects their thoughts and emotions. Similarly, mindfulness is a feature of Slow Looking in which the observer is prompted to consider not only what they see and how they feel, but also consider why, bringing their intuitive responses to conscious attention.

3.1.2 Cross-modal experience of audio and visual art

Previous work has investigated relationships between the perception of music and visual art. Limbert et al (1998) reported on a study in which participants observed a painting with either matching, non-matching or no music. Impressionist or abstract music was selected to either match or mis-match impressionist or abstract paintings. The aesthetic experience of viewing the paintings was found to be intensified when the paintings were accompanied with matching music. Palmer et al (2013) explored associations between music and color. Participants chose colors to fit different pieces of classical music. For both US and Mexican participants, faster major music was associated with saturated, lighter and yellower colours. Slower minor music was associated with desaturated, darker and bluer colours. A strong correlation was found between the emotions associated with matching colours and music, suggesting that music and colour association is mediated by emotion.

Albertazzi et al (2020) report on an experiment in which participants rated Kandinsky paintings and pieces of Schönberg music using Osgood semantic differential scales, rating the paintings and music as to extent to which they were, for example, fiery, warm or calm. They were also asked to match the paintings and pieces of music. Relationships were found between the ratings and the matches made between the paintings and pieces of music. Isaacson et al (2023) investigated how the perception of a painting can change when it is paired with music. Participants selected an artwork and then interpreted it, prompted by Slow Looking or visual thinking style questions (e.g. "What do you see?"). They then chose one of three musical pieces, pre-selected to match the painting, and repeated the interpretation exercise. The presence of music was found to enrich the interpretation with, for example, a heightened perception of narrative and movement in the painting.

Benford et al (2022) describe an emotional museum visitor experience called Sensitive Pictures. After choosing emotions associated with a painting on a web app, the visitor was instructed to locate it in the museum. Once they had found the painting, they played an audio dramatic fictional story offering an emotional interpretation of the painting. Visitors enjoyed the experience and

attributed their enjoyment to the enhanced emotional response provoked by the painting and accompanying audio story.

3.2 Deep Listening in the museum

3.2.1 Cross-modal experiences with a museum collection

The enhanced version of Deep Viewpoints was used by the musicologist to develop 11 scripts associating artworks with pieces of music. The musicologist did not approach the task from the point of view of a specific methodology but drew on her own teaching practice and her research into the paintings of Poussin and his use of musical modes (Barker 2000). Some scripts were motivated by associations between the artwork title and the title and/or lyrics of the music as in the case of *Eine Kleine Nacht Musick* described below. In other cases, an association was made between what is depicted in the artwork and the music, for example, the tree depicted in the artwork *The Music of Things (Sleep)* mentioned below. In many cases, the musicologist drew on her teaching experience of using visual cues such as colour and shape to help students understand elements of musical structure and engage in close or analytical listening without knowledge of music notation. An analysis of the structure and textual content of the scripts (described later section 6) helped to reveal the fine-grained ways in which the scripts were being used to associate music and visual art. Below this is synthesized into the main types of association on the overall level of the script.

Art interpretation providing context for interpretation of related music. One of the scripts started by offering an interpretation of the artwork *Il Trovatore* by Giorgio de Chirico. Explaining that the title translates as the troubadour, the script points to the long tradition of singing storytellers through to modern genres such as Rap. This set the scene for listening experiences with three varied pieces of music in the troubadour tradition.

The figure displays four screenshots of the IMMA Deep Viewpoints interface, each showing a different artwork and its associated music script. The interface includes a title bar, an image of the artwork, a description of the artwork, a question about the music, and a text input field for the user's response. Navigation buttons like 'Previous question', 'Next question', 'Continue', 'Back', and 'Close' are also visible.

- Screenshot 1: Eine Kleine Nacht Musick** by Joseph Cornell (1965). The question asks: "The title translates as 'a little night music'. What sort of sounds do you associate with the night? Are they comforting or scary?"
- Screenshot 2: View of Vetheuil** by Claude Monet (1880). The question asks: "Listen to this music thinking about the painting. What do you hear that might remind you of the countryside?"
- Screenshot 3: Lifting off from another world** by Kevin Mooney (2018). The question asks: "Does this song match your story?"
- Screenshot 4: Blighters Universe** by Kevin Mooney (2018-21). The question asks: "Does this song match your story?"

Figure 1: Example stages of the cross-modal scripts (from left to right): (1) a question stage asking the reader what sounds they would associate with the night, which is the subject of the artwork; (2) a multi-question stage asking a series of questions about a Monet artwork and a related piece of music chosen to evoke the countryside; (3) a statement stage using a piece of music by Brian Eno to interpret a Kevin Mooney artwork; and (4) a multi-question stage prompting the reader to build a story around a Kevin Mooney painting and then asking if the story matches the proposed music.

Using emotion to associate visual art and music. Four of the scripts supported the reader in making associations between music and visual art based on emotion. For example, one script guided the reader in looking at the artwork *Madonna and Child with Onlookers* by David Godbold and thinking about their emotional reaction to the painting. They were then asked to select which of two pieces of music matched their response to the artwork.

Imagining the look of a piece of music to make an association to visual art. Three of the scripts asked the reader to imagine what a piece of music might look like and then related what they imagined to visual art. For example, one script contained the musical piece *Walking the Dog* by George Gershwin. The reader was invited to take a paper and pencil and see what marks they made while listening to the song. The script then moved onto looking at related visual art.

Imagining the sound of an artwork to make an association to music. Four of the scripts involved imagining the sound of an artwork and then making an association to music. For example, one script considered the artwork *Eine Kleine Nacht Musick* by Joseph Cornell and Robert Cornell. The reader was asked to think about what sounds they associate with the night and also the cartoon-like mice in the artwork (figure 1, example 1). The script then moved on to consider the musical piece *Eine Kleine Nachtmusik* by Mozart.

Imagining both the look of music and sound of an artwork to create two-way associations. Three of the scripts involved two-way associations between music and visual art, that is, the three scripts that involved imagining the look of a piece of music also involved imagining the sound of an artwork. For example, one script started by looking at the artwork *Ancient Music* by Hughie O'Donoghue. The reader was asked to imagine what sounds were evoked by the image. The script moved onto a listening experience with two pieces of music and in turn imagining how these pieces of music could be represented visually, essentially closing the loop from art to music and back to art.

Synthesizing music into the experience of looking at visual art. One script involved listening to different pieces of music while looking at the same artwork and reflecting on how the music changed the personal response to what was seen. This script focused on the artwork *The Music of Things (Sleep)* by Alice Maher, which appears to depict singing heads suspended from a tree. The reader was asked to consider how two pieces of music changed the perception of the artwork (*Handel's Ombra mai fu* and *Strange Fruit* by Billie Holiday). This can be thought of as like the experiment of Isaacson et al (2023) which investigated how music changed the perception of a painting.

Synthesizing visual art into the experience of music listening. One script involved synthesizing visual art into the listening experience. The script began by looking at *View of*

Vetheuil by Claude Monet, which is a painting of a rural landscape. The reader was then asked to listen to an instrumental piece of music by Girolamo Frescobaldi, chosen because it is based on a melodic pattern that represents the call of the cuckoo, and identify anything they heard in the music that reminded them of the countryside. This can be thought of as the inverse of the experiment of Isaacson et al (2023) in which visual art and music are combined but, in this case, primarily to change or enhance the listening rather than the looking experience.

As described in the next section, the scripts authored by the musicologist were later used in a cross-modal experience for a youth group visiting a museum exhibition.

3.2.2 Cross-modal experiences with a museum exhibition

To investigate how cross-modal experiences could be integrated with a museum exhibition, an event was organized at IMMA for a youth group from the National Gallery of Ireland, called the Apollo Youth Panel. The event was structured in three parts.

The first part of the event explored looking and listening in the exhibition *Kevin Mooney, Revenants*, which, through a series of paintings, imagines the missing visual culture of Ireland lost to history due to poverty, famine and mass migration. Initially, the youth panel used the Slow Looking method to interpret the artwork *Mutators* by Kevin Mooney using typical questions such as “What do you notice first?”. The panel then moved onto the artwork *Ilcruthach* by Kevin Mooney. This time, interpretation was supported by three pieces of music played in the gallery while they looked at the artwork. Moody, dark and slow tempo music was selected to attempt to reflect the visual qualities of the painting. For the youth panel, *Piano Piece 1952* by Morton Feldman drew attention to the isolation and mood of the figure in the painting. There was a shared feeling of sympathy for the figure being all alone in the world. The song *Punisher* by dubstep artist Pinch was associated with the inferred heartbeat of the figure, imagining the body of the figure as pulsating. It was suggested that the first piece of music drew attention to the head and what the figure was thinking and feeling, whereas this song brought attention to the torso and how the heartbeat might make it move. Finally, the song *Te llevaré* by Lisandro Meza was associated with the legs of the character and how it might sway or walk in a slightly stilted way in keeping with the music. It was commented how the pieces of music had moved them from the head to the heart and legs of the figure.

The panel then moved onto the artwork *Blighters* by Kevin Mooney and its interpretation when accompanied by three further pieces of music. This time, music was selected on the basis of a conceptual connection to the subject of the painting, an imagined Irish diaspora. The three songs represented elements of diaspora or fusion between musical styles or cultures. With the song *Djelem Djelem* by Barcelona Gipsy Klezmer Orchestra, for the youth panel there was a focus on the mood of the song and a feeling that it reflected the sadness of the characters or their loneliness as the only survivors of some terrible event. The song *Ka Bohaleng / On the Sharp Side* by Abel Selaocoe evoked a more upbeat and optimistic interpretation. They felt that the song reflected the characters in the painting setting out on an adventure. They felt this could be thought of as the opening credits for a film about the characters as they are about to embark on their journey. It was commented how the music was helping to create a story around the artwork.

Finally, the song *The Wild Rover* by Lankum was perceived as a sadder song more appropriate for the closing credits to a film reflecting the end of the journey of the characters in the painting. Now the mood of the characters did not seem very positive. It was felt that maybe the journey had ended, and the mission had failed. It was commented once again that the music was helping to create a story around the painting.

There were three striking aspects of the in-gallery cross-modal experience. First, the combination of music and visual art could influence interpretation in two very different ways. The three pieces of music accompanying *Ilcruthach* by Kevin Mooney afforded a focus on parts of the character in the painting and the perception of movement. The three pieces of music accompanying *Blighters* by Kevin Mooney helped to situate the characters in the artwork within a narrative. Second, individual pieces of music could lead to markedly different interpretations, evoking movement in different parts of the character (in the case of *Ilcruthach*) or different narrative extensions of the characters (in the case of *Blighters*). Third, these differing interpretations, whether evoking movement or narrative, could have an emotional element which could be either positive or negative.

The second part of the event took part in a studio away from the exhibition and involved following the scripts developed by the musicologist. The panel worked in small groups using either their own smartphones or tablet computers supplied by the museum. The youth panel contributed 22 rich and varied responses to scripts. For example, the prompt on how the artwork *Ancient Music* would sound elicited responses including rain, slimy bugs, deep rumbling, organ and choir music and a musical piece that breaks to a softer tone. The artwork *Eine Kleine Nacht Musick* was associated with many different sounds including jazz, techno, classical, the weather, birdsong, and a lullaby. The cartoon-like mice in the artwork raised several associations including children's music, high-pitched, classical, piano, scurrying, jazz improv and squeaky music. The question of how to paint the musical piece *Eine Kleine Nachtmusik* by Mozart produced suggestions including zig zags, dancing on paper, swirling and rhythmic brushstrokes, vibrant and bright colours.

In the third part of the event the youth panel created their own cross-modal scripts in response to the Kevin Mooney, *Revenants* exhibition visited earlier in the day. Working in groups and using a combination of the museum tablet computers and their own smartphones, they developed 6 scripts. They can be broadly organized into three groups.

Using music for art interpretation. Three of the scripts used music as an integral part of a response to one of the artworks. For example, one of these scripts made associations between contrasts found in the musical work *An Ending (Ascent)* by Brian Eno and those found in the painting *Orbs* and other Kevin Mooney works (figure 1, example 3). Another of the three scripts used music to express something about a painting that could not easily be said. The script which included the artwork *Ilcruthach* by Kevin Mooney (interpreted earlier in the gallery), contained the text “This strange character evokes a number of emotions and ideas. These cannot always be represented through words, but rather an eerie feeling within.” This text was accompanied by the music *Title Theme of The White Lotus* by Cristobal Tapia De Veer.

Imagining the sound of an artwork to make an association to music. Two of the scripts guided the follower of the script to think about sounds associated with the artwork as well as

proposing their own musical association. One of the scripts was concerned with the artwork *Island* by Kevin Mooney. The script asks the reader what environmental sounds they would hear in this location and what sounds the mountain depicted in the painting would make. The script also makes an association between the artwork and the song *City made of code* by Sungmin Park. These two scripts can be thought of as like the musicological scripts that encouraged the reader to imagine the sound of an artwork to make an association to a piece of music.

Using narrative to associate visual art and music. One script used narrative to make an association between visual art and music. Starting with the painting *Blighters* by Kevin Mooney (interpreted earlier in the gallery), the script asked the reader a series of questions to build a narrative around the characters such as “Why are they here?”, “Who or what are they looking for?” and “What are they thinking about?”. Later the script proposes the music *Eyes Wide Open* by Gotye and asks, “Does this song match your story?” (figure 1, example 4). This can be thought as the inverse of the experience in the gallery, where pieces of music evoked a narrative. Here the script follower is encouraged to first develop a narrative and then consider a matching piece of music.

In the post-workshop discussion, the youth panel described the event as an immersive one, in which the music altered the viewing experience. They commented on how using the musicological scripts helped them to decide for themselves how they thought and felt about the visual artworks and music. When asked how the event could be improved or enhanced, they commented how the activity could be broadened further to include non-musical sounds and time for the drawing and painting of responses.

3.2.3 Analysis of the cross-modal scripts

The classification of the cross-modal scripts described in sections 4 and 5 was guided by an analysis of their structure and thematic content as described in sections 6.1 and 6.2 below.

Script structure

The scripts developed by the musicologist and youth panel had a similar length, on average comprising approximately three stages: 3.27 stages for the musicologist scripts and 2.67 stages for the youth panel scripts (table 2). The scripts developed by both the musicologist and youth panel provided opportunities for the script follower to contribute a response. In each case, statement stages (that do not invite a response) made up just 14% of the scripts. The total number of prompts was calculated as summing each question within a multi-question stage with the number of story and question stages. Overall, the scripts offered on average at least one prompt per script stage (1.39 prompts per stage for the musicologist scripts and 1.00 prompt per stage for the youth panel scripts). This suggests that the script authors adopted a contemporary approach to curation in line with the Slow Looking method, encouraging the script follower to develop their own response as well as engage with the interpretations of the script author. This finding is substantiated by the thematic analysis of the script text in section 6.2.

	Musicologist			Youth Panel		
	N	per script	per stage	N	per script	per stage
Scripts	11	1		6	1	
Stages	36	3.27	1	16	2.67	1
Statement	5	0.45	0.14	3	0.50	0.14
Question	18	1.64	0.50	9	1.50	0.43
Multiquestion	11	1.00	0.31	3	0.50	0.14
Story	0	0	0	1	0.17	0.05
Prompts	50	4.55	1.39	21	3.50	1.00

Table 2: Analysis of the scripts developed by the musicologist and youth panel.

Thematic analysis

The text contained in the scripts was classified in three ways. First, textual episodes were classified as to whether the script author was offering an interpretation to, or mediating an interpretation from, the script follower (table 3). In line with the analysis of script structure (section 6.1) numerous examples were found of mediation as well as interpretation. Second, an inductive approach (Birks and Mills 2014) was adopted to further identify categories within the episodes of interpretation and mediation. Six thematic categories were found: observation, artist, personal, perspectival, societal and imaginative (table 4). This range of categories was found across both the musicologist and youth panel scripts. The themes reveal additional ways of responding that can potentially be used to create associations between art and music. For example, as well as the viewer or listener reflecting on their personal response, they can also consider what the artist intended or what characters depicted in the art or music might be thinking or feeling, as part of their response.

Type	Examples
Interpretation: script author offering an interpretation to the reader	In the seventeenth century, Giulio Mancini, a famous doctor wrote about how gazing at landscape paintings and imagining walking in the landscape depicted in them was as good for the health as walking in the countryside.

Type	Examples
Mediation: script author assisting the reader to develop their own interpretation	Look at this painting. Using what you see as a starting point, what sensations do you imagine feeling if you walked in this landscape?

Table 3: Classifying episodes as interpretation and mediation.

Finally, an inductive approach (Birks and Mills 2014) was used to classify the episodes in terms of how they stayed within or transitioned between modalities (table 5). Examples were found that stayed within a single modality, that is, interpreting or mediating the looking at an artwork or the listening to a piece of music. The music episodes were found exclusively in the musicologist scripts. This may be due to the way the event was structured with the youth panel, with an initial focus on visual art. It may also reflect the musicologist's greater familiarity with the description of music. Two types of cross-modal episode were found in the scripts: creating a cross-modal response (i.e. imagining the sound of a painting or the look of a piece of music) and creating a cross-modal association (i.e. associating an artwork and piece of music or asking for a response to a proposed association). As described in sections 4 and 5, cross-modal creation and association were often used in combination within the scripts, for example inviting the follower of a script to imagine what a painting might sound like and then asking whether a particular piece of music fits with what they are imagining.

Type	Examples
Observation: an observation about the artwork or music	What are the first three words that come to mind when you look at this piece?
Artist: a view on the creator's intent, work or background	The artist called this picture, The Sound of Silence. Do you think he found silence peaceful, scary or neutral nothingness?
Personal: a personal view on what the artwork or music makes you think or feel	Do you trust this bizarre character? Are you threatened or comforted by its presence?
Perspectival: someone else's view such as that of a character in the artwork or music	Who or what are they looking for? What are they thinking about?
Societal: a societal and/or historical perspective related to the artwork or music	There are still singing storytellers today. There are a whole lot of modern genres that offer musical story telling about society – Blues, Rap etc.
Imaginative: an imaginative response to the artwork or music such as an answer to a creative question	Would you be scared by a giant spider? What would you do if it appeared next to you or if it bit you?

Table 4: Types of interpretation or mediation carried out. All examples shown are mediation, except the societal example which is interpretation.

Type	Examples
Visual art: Interpreting or mediating a piece of visual art	<p>What do you see in this picture (lines, colours, spaces)?</p> <p>Do the patterns make you respond emotionally or affect your mood?</p>
Music: Interpreting or mediating a piece of music	<p>What story do you think they are singing?</p> <p>What aspect of the music strikes you first?</p> <p>How does the music make you feel?</p>
Cross-modal creation: Creating a sound to match a piece of visual art or a visual to match a piece of music	<p>What kind of music, if any, come to mind when looking at the painting?</p> <p>What sounds do you think the mountain would make?</p> <p>If you were to draw or paint the music, what would it look like?</p>
Cross-modal association: Synthesizing or comparing a piece of visual art and a related piece of music	<p>Does this song match your story?</p> <p>This strange character evokes a number of emotions and ideas. These cannot always be represented through words, but rather an eerie feeling within. [Text accompanied by music]</p> <p>Listen to these two songs focusing on the words. After listening to each one, look again at the artwork. Does the artwork have a different mood for you now?</p>

Table 5: Modality of interpretation or mediation carried out.

3.2.4 Discussion of the in-museum study

This work has explored how Citizen Curation can be adopted by people outside the museum to use and create cross-modal experiences. The in-gallery event with the youth panel and analysis of the scripts created by the youth panel and musicologist reveal three ways in which music and visual art can be combined in cross-modal experiences: scene-setting, transition and synthesis. First, one modality can be used to set the scene for engagement in the other modality. One of the scripts used an artwork (Il Trovatore by Giorgio de Chirico) to introduce the concept of the

troubadour before listening experiences with thematically related music. The inverse could also be anticipated, in which music is introduced to set the scene for looking at related visual artworks. Second, Citizen Curation can be used to make a transition or mapping from one modality to the other. As revealed in the script analysis, one technique that can be used is to first imagine what an artwork might sound like and then use that imagery to make and evaluate associations to pieces of music. Similarly, the scripts reveal transitions in the inverse direction, guiding people to express what they see while listening to the music and then using that to test and make associations to works of visual art. The scripts also demonstrated that both can be amalgamated within a single experience, moving from one modality to other before returning. Third, like the work of Isaacson et al (2023), music and visual art can be synthesized into a combined looking and listening experience. For example, the script focused on *The Music of Things (Sleep)* by Alice Maher asked the reader to consider how two pieces of music changed perception of the artwork. Work in one modality can also be used directly in an interpretative response to work in the other modality. For example, the youth panel scripts revealed examples of using music as an interpretive response to visual art which perhaps could not be described in words.

Our work also showed how different characteristics can be used as a “glue” when associating music and visual art: emotion, narrative, theme and movement. Three of the scripts demonstrated how emotion can be used to connect music and visual art, reflecting on which pieces of music and visual art evoke a similar emotional response. This potentially connects to the work of Palmer et al (2013) (section 2.4) which suggests music and colour association is mediated by emotion. Narrative can be similarly used as a glue between music and visual art. The in-gallery event showed how music can help to evoke a narrative interpretation of art. One of the scripts created by the youth panel extended this idea by guiding the script follower to construct a story from an artwork which could then be compared against a piece of music. Theme or topic can be used to connect visual art and music. For example, the association of the painting *Orbs* with a Brian Eno piece (figure 1, example 3) makes a connection around the theme of reversal or contrast. The music relates to both landing and taking off. Relatedly, the viewer perceives both looking at and being looked at by the artwork. Movement can also be used in the association of visual art and music. During the in-gallery experience, the youth panel’s responses to *Ilcruthach* by Kevin Mooney drew on the imagined movement of the figure in the painting, related to the rhythmic qualities of the music. Imagined narrative and movement used to connect music and art may also itself have an emotional element.

What does the cross-modal experience reveal that might otherwise have been missed? In line with Isaacson et al (2023) our findings support the argument that music can help to heighten the perception of narrative and movement in visual art. Considering the inverse direction (visual art influencing listening) it could be argued that the perception of movement in visual art is drawing attention to the beat, tempo or rhythm of the music. Similarly, the narrative perception of visual art could be emphasizing the style or genre of the music. As well a potentially enhancing perception, feedback from the youth panel suggests that the cross-modal experience can be immersive. They also found the cross-modal scripts helped them to decide for themselves how they thought and felt.

3.3 Deep Listening online

3.3.1 Design of the study

The study in the museum demonstrated how the experiences of music and visual art can be combined into a looking and listening experience. The work suggested how the process of combining or synthesising the music and visual art could enable elements of the stimuli to be noticed or perceived in new ways. Four different types of “glue” connecting the music and visual art were observed: (i) emotion, narrative, theme and movement. The aims of online study were twofold. The first aim was to investigate in more depth the ways in which music and visual art are synthesized when experienced simultaneously, and how that may be affected by attributes of the music and visual art. For example, how might the emotional congruence between the visual art and music affect how and whether participants are able to synthesize them into a single experience? Emotional congruence between the two stimuli may assist in mentally synthesizing them. However, a lack of congruence, could potentially, create a challenge that leads to other, richer forms of association. The second aim was to find out how or whether cross-modal experiences could be supported in a purely online, distance context, away from the museum. This could indicate whether cultural organizations could offer such experiences online as well as whether they could be used in a distance education context for studies related to art and music appreciation.

To select a varied sample of music and visual art for use in the experiment, stimuli were chosen that varied in terms of their induced emotion. Four artworks were selected using the WikiArt dataset of emotions evoked by art (Mohammad and Kiritchenko 2018). This is a dataset of crowdsourced emotional responses to over 4000 artworks. Artworks are annotated using one or more of 20 emotion categories comprising positive emotions (e.g. gratitude, happiness, love) negative emotions (e.g. anger arrogance, disgust) and emotions categorised as mixed or other (e.g. anticipation, shyness, neutral). To select four varied artworks, the emotion categories were mapped to the circumplex model of emotion (Russel 1980) that positions emotions on a two-dimensional plane in which the horizontal axis is valence of the emotion (from negative to positive) and the vertical axis is level of arousal (from low to high) (see figure 2).

Four pieces of music were selected that were maximally distant from the upper and lower corners of the model. The four selected artworks were:

- CONTENTMENT: Portrait of a Man, Hugo van der Goes, circa 1480
- DEPRESSION: Anachorète endormi, Joseph-Marie Vien, 1751
- EXCITEMENT: Festivities on the Coast (Calendimaggio), Agostino Tassi, circa 1620
- DISTRESS: The Hippopotamus and Crocodile Hunt, Peter Paul Rubens, 1615–1616

Figure 2. Circumplex model of emotion adapted from Russel (1980).

Four pieces of music were selected in a similar way from the dataset of induced musical emotion (Aljanaki et al 2016). This dataset contains crowdsourced induced emotions for 400 musical excerpts. Participants annotated the musical excerpts with no more than 3 emotions from the Geneva Emotional Music Scale (GEMS) (Zentner et al 2008). The emotion categories used from GEMS were nostalgia, tenderness, amazement, solemnity, tension, joyful activation, power, sadness and calmness. Similarly to the artworks, the labels were mapped to the circumplex model and maximally distant pieces of music were selected from the upper and lower corners of the model based on their annotations.

The four selected musical excerpts were:

- CONTENTMENT: Rubber, Williamson. Album: A few things to hear
- DEPRESSION: Below, Lisa De Benedictis. Album: Tigers
- EXCITEMENT: Sunset (Endless Night Journey remix), DJ Markitos. Album: Evolution of the Mind
- DISTRESS: Ping Heng, Solace. Album: Balance

To provide an additional and varied array of musical samples. A further four pieces of music were selected by a musicologist. These were chosen based on their anticipated induced emotion rather than on empirical data. One-minute excerpts were selected from the four pieces to match the length of excerpts used with the musical emotion dataset. For reasons of copyright and so that the experiment could be conducted by participants independently online, the four excerpts were presented as embedded YouTube clips.

The four additional musical excerpts were:

- CONTENTMENT: Spiegel im Spiegel for Violin and Piano, Arvo Pärt
- DEPRESSION: Cry, Op. 27: I. Void - Light - Darkness, Giles Swayne
- EXCITEMENT: In The Upper Room: Dance No.9, Philip Glass
- DISTRESS: Threnody to the Victims of Hiroshima, Krzysztof Penderecki

The art and music selected for the experiment is summarized in table 6.

Arousal	Valence	Formally selected music	Musicologist selected music	Visual art
Low	Positive	Rubber, Williamson. Album: A few things to hear	Spiegel im Spiegel for Violin and Piano, Arvo Pärt	Portrait of a Man, Hugo van der Goes, circa 1480
Low	Negative	Below, Lisa De Benedictis. Album: Tigers	Cry, Op. 27: I. Void - Light - Darkness, Giles Swayne	Anachorète endormi, Joseph-Marie Vien, 1751
High	Positive	Sunset (Endless Night Journey remix), DJ Markitos. Album: Evolution of the Mind	In The Upper Room: Dance No.9, Philip Glass	Festivities on the Coast (Calendimaggio), Agostino Tassi, circa 1620
High	Negative	Ping Heng, Solace. Album: Balance	Threnody to the Victims of Hiroshima, Krzysztof Penderecki	The Hippopotamus and Crocodile Hunt, Peter Paul Rubens, 1615–1616

Table 6. Art and music selected for the experiment.

In the design of the experiment, it was decided to create an experience in which a participant would view one of the artworks without accompanying music and then look at the same artwork a further four times accompanied by a piece of music from each of the four quadrants of the emotion model, either those selected from the crowdsourced dataset of induced emotion or those selected by the musicologist. To balance for order effects, the order of the four pieces of music was randomized.

The procedure for the study was organized as a script of 9 stages within the Deep Viewpoints software. The stages were as follows:

[1] Introducing the aims of the study, ensuring anonymity and informing participants of their right to withdraw during the experiment.

[2] Collection of background and demographic data: age group, gender, frequency of looking at art, and frequency of listening to music.

[3] Looking at an artwork: describing what they notice and what they feel, rating how meaningful and pleasant they find the artwork.

[4..7] Looking and listening: Describing whether what they notice and how they feel has changed, describing any connections they make between the artwork and music, rating how connected they find the art and music, rating how meaningful and pleasant they find the experience. This step occurred four times each with a different piece of music presented in a random order.

[8] Feedback on the experience: Describing how helpful they found the experience to developing an appreciation for the artwork and giving any other comments they have about the experience.

[9] Submitting their response.

The experiment was supported by enhancements made to the software as described in section 3.2 of deliverable D5.3.

3.3.2 Preliminary findings and discussion of the online study

Initially, the experiment was run in a supervised mode in which the experimenter joined the participant on a Microsoft Teams call while they worked through the experiment. 18 participants across the 8 conditions took part in supervised mode. This was done to ensure the experiment was working appropriately before opening it up to unsupervised online participation. In this second stage, the invitation to participate was shared through the Polifonia project and Open University staff and student channels. 120 participants took part in unsupervised mode. The breakdown of participants is shown in table 7.

Visual art	Visual art arousal	Visual art valence	Music selection	Participants
Portrait of a Man, Hugo van der Goes, circa 1480	Low	Positive	Formally selected	19
Anachorète endormi, Joseph-Marie Vien, 1751	Low	Negative	Formally selected	16
Festivities on the Coast (Calendimaggio), Agostino Tassi, circa 1620	High	Positive	Formally selected	15
The Hippopotamus and Crocodile Hunt, Peter Paul Rubens, 1615–1616	High	Negative	Formally selected	16
Portrait of a Man, Hugo van der Goes, circa 1480	Low	Positive	Musicologist selected	20
Anachorète endormi, Joseph-Marie Vien, 1751	Low	Negative	Musicologist selected	20
Festivities on the Coast (Calendimaggio), Agostino Tassi, circa 1620	High	Positive	Musicologist selected	16

The Hippopotamus and Crocodile Hunt, Peter Paul Rubens, 1615–1616	High	Negative	Musicologist selected	16
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Table 7. Participants in the 8 experimental conditions.

Preliminary analysis of the data indicated that music brings new perspectives to the interpretation process. This is not necessarily concerned with participants noticing things in the artwork they did not previously see but rather seeing them in a new way of deriving different meanings from them. For example, there were multiple instances of something in the painting (such as a facial expression or action) being seen in either a positive (e.g. playful, fun) or negative (sinister, dangerous) way depending on the accompanying music. There were also multiple instances of the music drawing attention toward certain zones or elements of painting (and away from others).

Accompanying the same painting with multiple pieces music therefore enabled the painting to be seen from different perspectives and making different assumptions. This allowed them to cumulatively build a much richer picture of the painting. Rich and detailed responses to the experiment were elicited in both supervised and unsupervised mode, suggesting such an activity could support the independent, online appreciation of art and music.

Overall, feedback on the experience was extremely positive, with many participants responding unprompted how it had helped them to look and listen, develop their own interpretations, and reflect on how their interpretations could change across musical contexts.

Markedly different responses were found for different pairings of art and music. Ongoing analysis is being conducted to understand how the emotional congruence of the art and music affected the experience and the associations made.

Findings from the experiment will be taken forward to inform how cross-modal experiences can be used in both formal and informal educational contexts. From a formal education perspective, cross-modal interpretation could be used to support art and music appreciation courses. From an informal education perspective, the work could motivate guidelines for the design of exhibitions or activities that employ cross-modality to enrich the cultural experience.

4. Evaluating tools for transforming data to a Knowledge Graph

A task common across Polifonia pilots was transforming data from existing structured formats into RDF for inclusion in Knowledge Graphs. Structured data exists in a wide variety of formats, e.g. CSV, JSON, XML, and HTML. The need to convert this to RDF, for the creation of linked data, has stimulated the development of a variety of mapping techniques. There are two broad paradigms. One uses path descriptions, e.g. with JSONPath or XPath, to identify data elements. The other uses a default triplification which can be queried, e.g. with SPARQL.

An example of the use of path descriptions is R2RML (Das 2012), which was developed to map from relational database format to RDF. This was extended to RML (2014), which also maps from CSV, TSV, JSON and XML. For the latter two formats, RML makes use of JSONPath and XPath.

Subsequently, YARRRML (YARRRML), has been developed as a more human-friendly representation of R2RML and RML rules. Rules written in YARRRML are translated to RML, which is then used to map the source data to RDF.

An example of the use of triplification is SPARQL Anything (Daga 2021), which enables SPARQL to be used with structured data, e.g. CSV, JSON, XML, HTML, TXT and Markdown. The SERVICE operator is used to identify the source document and a default triplification of the whole document is created automatically, the structure of which depends on the format of the document. The WHERE clause is used to query the triplification. The CONSTRUCT clause is then used to create the required output RDF. Alternatively, a SELECT clause can be used to output query results rather than a graph, or an ASK clause can be used to determine the presence of matches to a query pattern.

We chose YARRRML as an example of the use of path descriptions because we believe it to represent the state-of-the-art from the viewpoint of usability of RML mappings generation; see Iglesias et al. (2023) for a recent comparison of user-friendly serializations for creating RDF. Similarly, we believe that SPARQL Anything represents the state-of-the-art for the triplification approach. Our goal was to recommend:

- i. rules and guidelines for users to create YARRRML and SPARQL Anything code;
- ii. future developments to YARRRML and SPARQL Anything to improve usability;
- iii. further areas of investigation and development for mapping techniques generally.

With regard to (i), we wished to investigate whether there are some use cases which are more appropriate for one or other of the two approaches.

4.1 Overview of the study and methodology

The study was a between-participants study with two conditions, i.e. one set of participants answered questions using YARRRML, the other set answered questions using SPARQL Anything. There were eight questions and these were the same in both conditions, in the sense that participants were presented with the same data files and with the same objectives. There were nine participants in the YARRRML condition, and nine in the SPARQL Anything condition. Participants were recruited from the Open University and from two W3C groups: the Knowledge Graph Construction Community¹ and the SPARQL 1.2 Community². Participants were free to choose whether to work with SPARQL Anything or YARRRML.

Some days before the study, participants were provided with a tutorial which explained all they needed to know about the technique they were to use. They were also provided with a document which explained how to download the necessary software and contained the eight questions which they would be requested to answer during the study. They were also sent the data files, as discussed in Section 4, and the question files, as discussed in Sections 5 and 6³. They were requested not to look at these questions until the session. In recruiting participants, it was

¹ <https://www.w3.org/community/kg-construct/>

² <https://www.w3.org/community/sparql-12/>

³ The tutorial, the question documents, and all the files sent out to participants are available at: https://ordo.open.ac.uk/articles/online_resource/Materials_for_mapping_study_structured_data_to_RDF/21476883

explained that the sessions would last one hour. At the beginning of each session, it was also explained that they might not answer all the questions in one hour, and that that was perfectly acceptable. Participants were also made aware that the study has been approved by the Open University's Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC/4195). Participants signed a consent form in which, apart from agreeing to take part in the study, they were also free to agree that their comments be quoted anonymously, or to withhold comments from publication. All agreed to their comments being quoted.

Before the study, participants were also sent a brief survey asking them about their previous experience with relevant technologies, and asking for some basic demographic information. Most participants were from Europe, with a few from the Americas and one from India. Ages varied from under thirty to over seventy, peaking at 40 to 49 years. There were 10 male and 8 female participants. At least six of the SPARQL Anything participants had a little, or more than a little, knowledge of SPARQL; only three had any knowledge of SPARQL Anything. Five of the YARRRML participants had a little, or more than a little, knowledge of RML or R2RML; only three had any knowledge of YARRRML. Eight of the participants classified themselves as software engineers; five as knowledge engineers; three as 'other'; and one did not specify role.

Each study was conducted over Microsoft Teams, with participants sharing their screen with the experimenter. There was a great deal of interaction between the participants and the experimenter; many participants found the exercises difficult and required assistance. This assistance ranged from 'hints', e.g. pointing out the presence of a square bracket denoting an array in JSON, to provision of the solution, which was then explained. Participants were also provided with files containing the required output RDF, although only a few participants referred to these. Only three of SPARQL Anything and four of the YARRRML participants completed all eight questions, although most completed the first five. Many participants spent more than the proposed hour on the study. Each session was recorded, using the Microsoft Teams recording facility and then analyzed using the NVivo qualitative analysis tool⁴.

For reasons of time, and because we were chiefly interested in the conceptual, rather than the syntactic, difficulties experienced by the participants, we did not expect participants to create solutions from scratch. Instead, as is explained in more detail in Sections 5 and 6, we provided partial solutions and asked participants to complete the gaps. We then analyzed the recordings to create a grounded classification of the observed errors, informed by the participants' comments⁵. This was inevitably a subjective process. We only make approximate attempts to quantify the importance of each error. In particular, an appreciable number of the participants found many of the questions very difficult and required considerable guidance, making rigorous quantification of errors impossible.

⁴ Supplied by QSR International: <https://www.qsrinternational.com>

⁵ For a description of grounded theory, see [30].

Figure 3. Flowchart illustrating stages of analysis

4.2. Study materials

Questions 1 and 2 used a slightly modified version of a JSON file which described an artwork in the Tate Gallery in London⁶. We chose a real, and relatively complex, example to ensure ecological validity. The file uses nested objects and arrays to provide information about the artwork, including characterizing the file with 13 topics. Each topic has a numeric id and a name. The topics are arranged hierarchically, in four levels. At the top-level there is one overarching topic, with id “1” and name “subject”. We modified this file slightly: by re-ordering the information, to present the topic hierarchy top-down, and thereby improve readability; by renaming the overarching topic “topicRoot”, to avoid any possibility of confusion with the word “subject” in the context of RDF triples or YARRRML mappings; by changing the JSON object “contributors” to “creator” and reducing the information provided about the creator.

Question 1 was a straightforward question to test the basic understanding of the YARRRML or SPARQL Anything approaches, and to introduce participants to the study process. Question 2 used the JSON file in conjunction with the CSV file, which contains information about five artists. The goal of question 2 was to create one triple with subject the url of the artwork, which is contained in the JSON file; and with object the url describing the artist, which is contained in the CSV file.

Questions 3, 4 and 5 all had the same objective, to create two sets of twelve triples. One set had as subject the *url* of the artwork, and as object an IRI of the form *tsub:id*, where each id was an id describing the artwork. The predicate was to be *schema:about*. The other twelve triples required each *tsub:id* as subject, and the corresponding topic name as object. The predicate was to be *schema:name*. Question 3 used the JSON file. Question 4 used an XML file containing the same information as, and a similar structure to, the JSON file. Question 5 also used an XML file but this time making use of XML attributes.

Questions 6, 7 and 8 also had the same objective, and used the JSON file and the two XML variants. The objective of this question was to create 12 triples describing the links in the topic

⁶ The original JSON file is available at: <https://github.com/tategallery/collection/blob/a51d8afc988ed083557e2950f4d0b644e7719f4a/artworks/a/000/a00002-1036.json>

hierarchy, i.e. the subject of each triple was a topic, and the object was a child topic. The predicate was to be *skos:broader*.

Q	Purpose of question	YARRRML requirements	SPARQL Anything requirements
1	Use the basic features of the two paradigms. Participants were required to generate an output file with triples created from a CSV and a JSON file.	Understand the structure of a mapping statement. However, there was no requirement to use a condition.	Create predicates of the form <i>xyz:<CSV column header></i> and <i>xyz:<JSON name></i>
2	Create a conditional join.	Use equal function, identifying which parameters come from the source and object mappings.	Understand role of FILTER statement to create a join, and of IRI() function to create an IRI from a string.
3, 4, 5	Negotiate a hierarchical data structure, creating two sets of triples: one with items (ids and names) at the same level; the other associating a stated item (artwork) with all the topic ids in the hierarchy.	Use of JSONPath, XPath and recursive descent.	Understand the difference between the triplication of JSON and XML. In particular, understand the different treatment of XML tags and attributes. Understand where one can use, e.g. <i>rdf:_1</i> , and where it is necessary to use a variable to bind to <i>rdf:_1</i> , <i>rdf:_2</i> etc.
6, 7, 8	Negotiate a hierarchical data structure, linking each id with its immediate 'children' ids.	Similar to questions 3, 4, 5. However, care needs to be taken to link parent ids only to immediate children ids, i.e. not all children ids.	

Table 8 Purpose of questions and required knowledge of YARRRML and SPARQL Anything

4.3 YARRRML user behaviours

Table 9 shows the error categories. With one exception, all or almost all of our participants made an error in each category. The exception was YARRRML syntax and semantics. As previously explained, the questions were constructed to reduce difficulties with using and interpreting YARRRML syntax; even so over half of our participants had difficulties.

Error	Examples
Iterator Errors (N = 9)	Iterator path too long, so that it cannot concatenate with path in a value statement to form correct JSONPath.
	Iterator path too short, so that there is a 'gap' when the iterator path is concatenated with a path in a value statement.
	Iterator path too short, and path in subject and object value statements too long, so that whilst they concatenate to form a valid JSONPath, the subject and object do not necessarily correspond.
	Not starting iterator from root of document, or with a recursive descent.
Recursive descent errors (N = 9)	Placing recursive descent in a value statement when it should be in the iterator. This can have a variety of effects, e.g. leading to no triples or too many. A variant on this is placing recursive descent in both the iterator and a value statement, when it should only be in the iterator.
	Omitting recursive descent when it is required, which can have the effect of creating only a subset of the required triples.
	Failing to realize that recursive descent can be used at the beginning of a path statement, to subsume the beginning of the path, rather than later in the statement. This causes unnecessarily long path statements.
Path syntax errors (N = 9)	Not taking account of JSON arrays.
	Misuse of dot in JSONPath: either including a leading dot (<i>.creator.id</i>) or omitting a dot (<i>\$topics</i>).
	Failure to use @ to identify an attribute in XPath; alternatively, when @ was used, failure to place a / before the @, i.e. writing <i>topic@id</i> rather than <i>topic/@id</i> .
	Confusion between JSONPath and XPath, e.g. between . and / as separators and \$ and / to indicate the document root.
Path errors, i.e. other than syntax errors (N = 8)	Path too short to uniquely specify data.
	Missing element in path.
	Failure to understand form of required triple.
	Copying JSON value rather than JSON name.

Error	Examples
Misunderstanding question or data (N = 8)	Failure to understand nature of the data.
YARRRML syntax and semantics errors (N = 5)	Failure to understand purpose of mapping statement, i.e. that it needs to contain the name of a mapping.
	Failure to understand the significance of <i>s</i> and <i>o</i> in the join condition, and confusion about the role of the parameters <i>str1</i> and <i>str2</i> .
	Confusion between the use of quotes in the iterator but not in the value statement.
	Confusion potentially caused by use of <i>\$</i> in JSONPath and in YARRRML syntax.

Table 9. YARRRML errors made by participants

4.4 SPARQL Anything – user behaviours

Table 10 shows the major error categories. As with Table 9, care needs to be taken in interpreting the numbers in the table, because of the great deal of assistance given to some participants. Moreover, it is not always possible to be precise about the nature of the problem; in particular between problems in understanding the nature of the triplification and the structure of the data.

Error	Examples
SPARQL errors (N = 8)	Difficulties with square bracket notation, e.g. writing <code>[] [...]</code>
	Difficulties with variable names, e.g. failure to understand need to create a new variable to be argument of <code>STR()</code> in questions 3, 4 and 5.
Graph pattern errors (N = 7)	Failing to understand when a blank node should be shared between graph patterns.
	Omitting an XML element or JSON object or array element in the path to the required datum.
	Ignoring JSON arrays.
	Failing to understand that a graph pattern can start from anywhere, not necessarily the root of the document.
Misunderstanding question or data (N = 7)	Failure to understand form of required triple.
	Failure to understand the data, e.g.: missing an element in an XML hierarchy, failure to discriminate between different uses of <i>id</i> in the data (creator id and topic id); or (in question 5) failure to understand the need for a new blank node on the second line to be completed.
Triplification errors (N = 6)	Failing to translate correctly from data to triplification, e.g. with nested data omitting a level.
	Confusing the two forms of triplification: JSON objects and XML attributes, versus XML elements.
Misuse of <i>rdf:_1</i> (N = 5)	Failing to note the need for a variable, rather than <i>rdf:_1</i> , where variable needs to bind to <i>rdf:_1 ... rdf:_n</i> , as with JSON arrays or XML elements.

Table 10. SPARQL Anything errors made by participants

4.5 Comparing the paradigms

The two paradigms are quite different, and require different expertise and understanding. The essential requirements to use YARRRML are familiarity with path statements, e.g. JSONPath and XPath and to understand the role of the iterator. YARRRML is a subset of YAML, so some prior familiarity with YAML is useful. YARRRML is intended as a more human-readable alternative to RML. However, arguably it may be useful in debugging to at least be able to read RML. On the other hand, the essential requirements to use SPARQL Anything are familiarity with SPARQL syntax and semantics and to understand the particular triplification used. This means that some of the problems experienced by the two sets of participants seem quite different. However, in both cases the most fundamental problems have their roots in the same issues relating to the

data. In particular, in our study, the need to negotiate hierarchical data created difficulties. For YARRRML, this meant that participants needed to understand how to use recursive descent. For SPARQL Anything, this meant that they had to understand how to construct a graph pattern that matched appropriately at various levels of the hierarchy.

How users find the advantages and disadvantages of the two paradigms will depend on their backgrounds. Those very familiar with JSONPath and XPath will have an advantage when starting to use YARRRML. Those very familiar with SPARQL will have an advantage when starting to use SPARQL Anything. However, an advantage of YARRRML over SPARQL Anything is that users of the former need only be familiar with the data and their required output RDF. Users of SPARQL Anything need also to be familiar with the triplification. On the other hand, once that triplification is understood, it is relatively easy for users to modify the SPARQL to make changes to the output, or simply to explore the data. Indeed, it is possible to explore the data without being fully aware of its structure, and of the triplification. One could, for instance, determine all the predicates in the triplification of a JSON file, thereby identifying all the names used in the file. Alternatively, with a triplification of XML, one could inspect the objects of all triples with predicates `rdf:type` to determine the tags used in the XML.

For YARRRML, the difference between JSON and XML resides in the difference between the JSONPath and XPath syntaxes. For SPARQL Anything, the difference is more fundamental, since XML tags are used to create class names. This not only creates a difficulty in moving between JSON and XML, but also makes for a greater complexity when dealing with XML, as we have noted in subsection 8.1.

It may be that YARRRML has an advantage where the required RDF is specified once and for all. Here an approach which avoids the intermediate stage of a triplification may be preferred. On the other hand, SPARQL Anything may have an advantage where we are unsure precisely what form the final output should take, or want to explore the data. In this case, the overhead of understanding the triplification will be worthwhile. We summarize our comparison in Table 11.

	YARRRML	SPARQL Anything
Users need expertise in ...	Path statements, e.g. JSONPath and XPath; also some understanding of YAML. Ability to read RML may be useful in debugging.	SPARQL syntax and semantics.
Users need to understand ...	The role of the iterator and how to use path statements.	The triplification.
	The use of recursive descent to negotiate the hierarchy.	How to construct a graph pattern to match at various levels of the hierarchy.

Advantages	Need only be familiar with data and required output, i.e. no intermediate stage.	Easy to change SPARQL to make changes to output or to explore the data.
Disadvantages	Not so easy to change required output and to explore the data.	Need to be familiar with triplification, which can be complex and differs for JSON and XML.
Recommended usage	Use cases where the output is fixed once and for all.	Use cases where ability to explore the data and flexibility in varying the output is required.

Table 11. Comparison of YARRRML and SPARQL Anything

5. Conclusions

This deliverable provides a report on user interaction evaluation work conducted within task 5.1 of the project. The deliverable started by describing the support given to pilots in validating their work from a user interaction perspective. The rest of the deliverable described studies of user interaction carried out within task 5.1. First, we described two studies into the process of cross-modal interpretation (termed Deep Listening) in which the user creates or makes sense of an experience combining music and visual art. The first study was conducted at a museum and involved participants in both creating and use cross-modal experiences. The second study was conducted online and investigated the types of association made between the music and visual art during cross-modal experiences. Finally, the deliverable reported on an evaluation of tools for translating data into a Knowledge Graph, including SPARQL Anything which was extensively used within the project.

Compliance to the FAIR principles

This section encompasses information which helps to the knowledge management in the project and to make Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Deep Listening/Deep Viewpoints

Type: Experimental materials

In accordance with ethical requirements, once the data has been analysed and anonymisation ensured, the raw data and study materials will be made available in in a publicly accessible repository with version control.

Evaluating data transformation tools

Type: Experimental materials

All materials required to run the experiment are in a publicly accessible repository with version control. The materials can be found at https://ordo.open.ac.uk/articles/dataset/Materials_for_mapping_study_structured_data_to_RDF/21476883

Due to anonymisation requirements the raw data videos of participants taking part in the study cannot be shared.

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